

PREDICTING EMERGING MARKET RETURNS WITH SIMPLE MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES

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Abstract

This study applies simple machine learning techniques to predict Emerging Market (EM) equity returns. It examines excess returns for major EM indices versus relevant benchmarks. Predictor variables were drawn from the same security's historical excess returns. The intuition is that past performance can be predictive of future investment interest and that predictive relationship is unique for each security. Therefore, a variety of models need to be considered. A total of five models were applied: traditional logistic regressions, ridge, random forest, boosting and neural nets. The results indicate that newer machine learning-based predictive relationships, such as random forest, boosting, and neural nets, generate valuable out-of-sample results. In nearly all countries, there was a machine learning active strategy that delivered higher returns than a passive long strategy. The paper identifies avenues for further exploration of such investment strategies.

Keywords: emerging markets, machine learning, international investing, momentum.

The shift of investment flows from active managers to passive vehicles has turned into a deluge in recent years. This move has been driven by, among other things, low fees for passive vehicles and lackluster performance by active managers. However, most passive funds utilize a naïve long-only market capitalization based approach to investing and then optimize for the lowest possible trading cost. Emerging “smart-beta” products (e.g. Momentum or Value) are based on universal factors that have been back-tested excessively, with limited application of modern data mining techniques. New developments in machine learning allow for multiple levels of abstraction that supersede the complex regression modeling even from a few years ago, let alone beat subjective heuristics that active managers or passive index rules often rely on.

Using EM index excess returns

The focus on excess returns for emerging market indices is unique for four reasons.

Longer time horizons: Many large algorithmic firms focus on very high frequency trading (e.g. at the tick-level). The statistical relationships and proposed investment strategies are much longer term in nature. In other words, they are “playing” in a different world for even the same security.

Emerging Market coverage: EM tends to have less investment coverage given its smaller size, lower liquidity, political risks and difficulty marketing such funds to Western investors. In fact, emerging markets investing is still seen as a “boots-on-the-ground” endeavor, a self-fulfilling prophecy that means there is more to be explored quantitatively in this space.

Relative Returns: using excess returns for a security over its higher-level aggregate benchmark further narrows the scope of analysis. Such an approach seeks to derive information from the top-down country allocation approach that international investors implicitly use.

Indices: Using broad-based index returns instead of single stocks adds diversification. It also mitigates the potential for a machine learning's strategy's “edge” to be competed away soon. The overall equity market for a country or region has a plethora of participants with varied motivations, only some of whom will ever

invest based on an algorithm even if presented with a 99% accurate one. In other words, there are natural limits to arbitraging away such strategies at the total stock market level. In addition, index returns can also be replicated easily today using low-cost liquid ETFs or futures.

Using historical returns

This analysis is inspired from research by Krauss, Do, and Huck (2016), Takeuchi and Lee (2013), Moritz and Zimmerman (2014). All these studies apply machine learning techniques to individual stocks in either the S&P 500 or US CRSP database. In particular, they use various horizons of past daily performance to predict future returns, with an inherent emphasis on momentum philosophies. Asness, et al. (2014) lay out the basis for momentum's centuries-long performance as a source of sustainable and meaningful investment returns. Habauer, et al. (2023) have used machine learning models on individual EM stocks rather than indices to show the superior forecasting ability of machine learning relative to traditional linear models. As a variant to this, this paper analyzes excess returns for individual indices, rather than create a portfolio that requires daily rebalancing of individual stocks. With the growth of futures and liquid ETF vehicles aiming to replicate country stock indices, this index-based approach may be more practical and diversified for a broad array of financial practitioners.

Using monthly data

Although weekly data can greatly expand the number of observations, monthly data has a few advantages. Cross-country allocations are often driven by medium-term political and economic views. Reducing the frequency can remove noise associated with intramonth gyrations. Monthly data also reduces transaction costs from higher frequency trading. Finally, this approach aligns with the monthly rebalancing schedule followed by major ETFs.

Data extraction, cleanup and summary

The dataset is extracted from Thomson Datastream's MSCI database (Morgan Stanley Country Indices). These are indices that track the global equity market levels and are the most commonly-used benchmarks for index funds and institutions. The index levels

are extracted monthly and denominated in US dollars to provide a common standard. The indices used are calculated on a total return basis, i.e. dividend are included.

The MSCI World index is the developed country index, representing large and mid-cap equities that covering approximately 85% of the free float in each of the 23 constituent countries. The index tends to be very highly correlated with US S&P 500 index, not a surprise given the 73% weight to the US. The next largest countries are Japan and the UK at 5.2% and 3.6% respectively.

The MSCI Emerging Market index is made up of 24 emerging market nation indices, covering approximately 85% of the free float in each country again. This index represents 10% of global market capitalization, up from 1% in 1988 when it was launched. The index is heavily dominated by Asia. The top four countries - China, Taiwan, India and Korea - comprise around 75% of the index. While the index was launched in 1988, the larger countries in the current index were only added in the mid-to-late 1990s.

The definition of Emerging Market used here is based solely on western investor behavior and MSCI index rules. There are many dimensions across which it would be inappropriate to label these countries developing, e.g. China's share of global GDP/trade or Korea's per capita income.

Response and predictor variable creation

For clarity's sake, the model is applied solely to the aggregate Emerging Market index. First, a return stream is created for the excess return of emerging over developed markets. The next month's value of excess return is considered to be the response variable, transformed into a binomial i.e. if the excess return is greater than zero, the response variable is 1 and 0 otherwise.

The predictor variables are generated as trailing differences at various horizons. The study selects months 1 through 12, and then 6 months intervals out to 3 years for sensibilities sake, to get a total of 16 predictors.

To visualize this, say one is looking at the June 2015 datapoint. EM outperformed DM in the next month, July 2015, so the response value = 1. X_1 = 1-month (June 2015) return of EM less 1-month (June 2015) return of DM, X_2 = 2-month return of EM less 2-month return of DM, ...and so on until X_{16} = 3-year return of EM less 3-year return of DM, both ending June 30 2015.

This format can then be extended to each EM country relative to overall EM. For instance, Brazil's response variable will be 1 if Brazil's return is greater than EM the following month. And the predictor variables will be Brazil less EM returns at various horizons.

Splitting observations

Three methods for splitting data were considered (using a standard 75/25 split): Chronological, Random Sampling and Rolling Windows. The final choice was to use Chronological, but it is relevant to discuss the merits and concerns of each approach.

Chronological: The chronological split sets the train data from 1999 through mid-2019 and test data

from then until 2024 (roughly 5 years to capture a cycle). Inherently this means that one is making a prediction based on historical relationships. The advantage of chronological splitting is that it allows one to logically calculate hypothetical performance statistics for an investment strategy based on these results.

Random Sampling: One alternative was to use a random sample of monthly observations that ignored the chronological time nature. This would mean using future data points to predict past ones. Unintuitive as it sounds, this wouldn't be problematic because it identifies the predictive relationship of a security to its past return structure. It assumes that this relationship is independent of time. In fact, this would allow one to make a more "universal" or "evergreen" model for that specific security and not limit training (or testing) time period. One concern is that performance statistics from this would be erroneous. The performance statistics require a chronological time series and one cannot use the randomized serial numbers for that.

Rolling Windows: A rolling window would maintain chronological nature of the data. For instance, one could split data into 7.5 years training and the next 2.5 years test, repeatedly at intervals starting each calendar year. This would provide around 25 iterations of each model and 25 train/test errors, which could then be averaged to provide a final error estimate. The model's continuous updating will account for changing secular market regimes by basing predictions on the recent past. The challenge here is that more observations are needed and monthly numbers limit the scope for this. In addition, each time the model is losing data from old time periods that may have predictive power for the future.

Models

5 models were used. First, a **simple logistic regression** against all the variables. Second, a **ridge regression** to regularize the variables, i.e. shrink the size of the coefficients by adding a penalty for a higher number of variables introduced. The third model is a **random forest**, which breaks the data into trees along randomly selected variables (5 randomly selected out of the total 15), majority vote within any tree node (minimum node size is 10 observations), and repeats this 500 times by using bagging (resampling with replacement). The fourth model was **boosting**, which begins with a weak model and then iteratively estimates the remaining error to improve the model's predictive power. The starting weak model was a simple decision tree with 3 splits. For each security, it found the optimal number of iterations to fit the final boosting model. The model's target was set to minimize classification error. Finally, a **neural net** model was applied, that uses a sigmoid function repeatedly to estimate our response variable. This version uses 2 layers of 5 and 3 neurons for the neural net.

Results

The misclassification errors for the models over the test period are provided below. Misclassification error is the percentage of times the predicted performance (i.e. excess return > or <0) does not match the actual result next month.

Exhibit 1: Results

	Simple Logistic	Ridge	Random Forest	Neural Net
EM*	62%	62%	59%	50%
Thailand	56%	59%	50%	53%
China	45%	62%	45%	52%
Korea	36%	50%	41%	41%
Taiwan	50%	42%	55%	62%
Malaysia	45%	44%	50%	39%
Thailand.1	56%	61%	50%	53%
India	50%	52%	47%	50%
Indonesia	58%	55%	55%	52%
SoAf	50%	45%	53%	48%
Poland	52%	50%	45%	48%
Brazil	50%	50%	36%	45%
Mexico	41%	47%	58%	48%
Chile	45%	47%	56%	45%
Turkey	47%	55%	59%	47%

*EM vs DM; Rest are Country vs EM

In general, the random neural net performs very well. Given the very low significance of individual variables in the regression approaches, we're more inclined to use either random forest or neural net. Random forests have very low training errors that could indicate overfitting due to the small number of observations. To mitigate this, the minimum nodesize was set to 10 versus the default 1 typically used for classifications.

The value in being able to run these alternative models against each security is that one does not need

to pick a universal approach. For certain securities, neural net does a better job and for others, random forest (e.g. see Poland and Brazil). Moreover, even with the same model, e.g. random forest, the variables that are most important can vary by security. E.g. the charts below are variable importance plots from the random forest models for EM and Malaysia. The former is driven most by the 1-month return and the latter by the 2-year return.

Exhibit 2: Random Forest: Variable Importance Plots

Brazil

Malaysia vs EM

In comparison to human active management that finds it extremely difficult to beat naïve passive indices, our model errors less than 50% have the potential to be developed into powerful investing strategies. Of course, such potential is subject to the distribution of returns for a given security. Analysis and comments on that provided in the next section.

Investment Performance

Investment strategies were created based on all the models. The strategy goes long when the next month is

predicted to have positive excess returns and short otherwise. This is compared against performance of a passive strategy that stays long the security. In all these cases one is going long one security vs the other (i.e. these are all relative returns).

A summary performance table is below along with a chart for the EM vs DM performance (additional charts in appendix). On a country by country basis, no one model is robust across the countries. However, certain models jump out as generating very strong returns

for a given country, which ties back to a point in the previous section that each security is unique in its relationship to past returns. Therefore, model selection can be done on a security-by-security basis rather than to create universal market truths. For EM vs DM as a

whole, neutral net deliver top results. The only two countries where machine learning techniques do not generate a higher-value strategy vs passive long are Taiwan and India – notice that these 2 have also been outlier strong performers within the group.

Exhibit 3: Performance (Annualized, test period)

	Passive Long	Simple Logistic	Ridge	Random Forest	Neural Net
EM*	-8.6%	-9.0%	-12.3%	-8.0%	2.7%
Thailand	-7.4%	-8.4%	-7.4%	-1.9%	-1.3%
China	-4.2%	4.6%	-4.2%	-6.6%	-6.0%
Korea	-1.5%	12.1%	-0.4%	9.9%	8.7%
Taiwan	12.5%	2.9%	6.5%	-3.4%	-11.3%
Malaysia	-3.2%	-1.1%	1.7%	-0.8%	7.0%
India	8.5%	-2.6%	-3.1%	0.8%	-11.8%
Indonesia	-5.3%	-11.6%	-3.9%	-8.1%	0.9%
SoAf	-0.4%	-7.3%	-2.4%	-7.4%	1.0%
Poland	-3.7%	-1.4%	0.2%	4.9%	7.5%
Brazil	-7.1%	-0.8%	0.4%	26.9%	3.0%
Mexico	1.6%	10.7%	-6.0%	-16.2%	8.8%
Chile	-6.7%	6.6%	1.9%	-8.0%	3.8%
Turkey	1.8%	7.0%	1.8%	-19.4%	-7.5%

*EM vs DM; Rest are Country vs EM

Ignores transaction costs, which should be minimal given liquid ETFs and monthly rebalancing

	top model vs passive	top model
EM*	11%	nn
Thailand	6%	nn
China	9%	glm
Korea	14%	glm
Taiwan	-6%	ridge
Malaysia	10%	nn
India	-8%	rf
Indonesia	6%	nn
SoAf	1%	nn
Poland	11%	nn
Brazil	34%	nn
Mexico	9%	glm
Chile	13%	glm
Turkey	5%	glm

Exhibit 4: EM vs DM performance chart

Scaling

The models predict a probability for whether the next month's excess return is positive or not. A simplifying assumption was used here that if the predicted probability exceeded 50%, go long and otherwise go short. One approach to improve this could have been to scale the long/short positions based on the probability itself rather than using the arbitrary 50% threshold. Another option would be to choose a threshold based on risk tolerance. e.g. if one is more fearful of sharp negative moves, one would want to minimize false positives and maximize true negatives, so choose a threshold greater than 50%.

Taking a step back from the classification approach, one could also treat next month's returns as a continuous response and use a least square error loss function. Scaling of investments could then be done by standardizing (z-score) the mean square error for each observation.

Conclusion

This research can be used by investors to access superior returns that are difficult to arbitrage away, and a unique algorithmic strategy that adds to portfolio diversification. Index firms can use this to expand their product menu and cater to the nascent demand for machine learning based investment products. It could also be used by active managers as a trading indicator to supplement or diversify their own fundamentals-based research. Such diversification might be particularly val-

uable for emerging market funds. Individual quantitative investing enthusiasts can use this research as a stepping stone for further study and investing.

The results should provide more light on the predictive power of newer machine learning techniques. There are many avenues for further exploration: data frequency, replacing X_i s with different horizons/risk metrics, incorporating lasso, splitting, scaling, and extending this framework to other securities. In conclusion, if one believes that each security's relationship to its past returns is unique and relatively stable over large periods of time, there is no need to be straightjacketed by a one-size-fits-all factor model across those securities.

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